

“The Truths We Hold: An American Journey” – A daughter’s leadership journey shaped by the scientific method

In her 2019 book, the current Vice President and candidate for the presidency of the United States demonstrates how women can disrupt entrenched systems in fields dominated by white men. Her story illustrates the benefits of growing up with a scientist as a mother.

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No matter where you live in the world, you have most likely heard of Kamala Harris, the first female, Southeast Asian, and black Vice President of the United States. She is also the Democratic candidate for the presidency. Harris is the daughter of immigrants who met as graduate students at the University of California at Berkeley. Her father, Donald Harris, was born in Jamaica and eventually became a professor of Economics at Stanford University. Her mother, Shyamala (née) Gopalan, was born in Southern India, and became a breast cancer researcher in the US and Canada. Her parents’ story reminds us that one of the great privileges of a STEMM career is the ability to work with students and professionals from around the globe. Rather than following in her parents’ STEMM footsteps, Harris decided to pursue a law degree, beginning her career in the Alameda County (CA, USA) District Attorney’s Office, and eventually pursuing various political positions—even the highest in the land.

Why is it worth taking the time to read her book, “The Truths We Hold: An American Journey” [1]? Although Harris’ life story may not appear at first glance to be relevant to senior women leaders in STEMM, the book holds many valuable lessons for and about women leaders. Moreover, no matter your nationality or political views, her story is a testimonial to the power of women scientists as parents and mentors, whether or not young people choose to pursue science, themselves.

Many of our prior posts have discussed how women, because of their different life experiences, can bring new perspectives and ideas to leadership positions. This point is especially highlighted in our post about the near-universal benefits of [supporting women in the workplace](#) [2] and our [review](#) of “The Moment of Lift” by Melinda French Gates [3]. Systems can easily become entrenched, even when they are no longer working for some individuals or the population as a whole. Because of her multi-racial, multi-ethnic, middle-class upbringing, Harris recognized how the criminal justice system in her hometown, her state, and ultimately her nation could be transformed to serve the people more effectively and efficiently. As a woman, Harris recognized

the (sometimes disproportionate) impacts on women of issues of social and economic justice. Her mother taught her to “*Fight systems in a way that causes them to be fairer, and [not to] be limited by what has always been.*”

Prosecutors in the US are predominantly white men. Harris demonstrated early on that, when a woman of color steps into those positions, she can ‘think outside the box’ to find new solutions to age-old problems. For example, when Harris was elected to head San Francisco District Attorney’s office, she started a transformational program to help young, non-violent first-time offenders get their lives ‘back on track’ through intensive work, education, and community service. Not only did this program greatly decrease re-offense rates, it saved taxpayers substantial money by reducing incarceration and further prosecution. Later in her career, she developed the first programs to train law enforcement officers in the problems of implicit bias and how to avoid them.

Harris writes about initially running for District Attorney: “*I had to run because I knew I could do the job—and I believed I could do it better than it had been done. Still, I knew I represented something bigger than my own experience. At the time, there weren’t many district attorneys who looked like me or had my background. There still aren’t.*”

We believe that many academic departments, and entire universities, also could benefit from some constructive disruption led by women and/or people of color. In the US, the cost of a college education has become too expensive for many students, who may forego higher education or graduate with staggering student debt. While some STEMM disciplines offer the promise of high-paid jobs, many do not. Moreover, what happens if a student becomes ill or discovers too late that they have not made the best career choice? Throughout the world, women in STEMM are often relegated to lower paid technician or untenured teaching positions, and the biological clock often conflicts with the need to build one’s STEMM career during one’s child-bearing years. The huge amounts of unpaid labor that women perform both at work and at home exacerbates the challenges of balancing professional and personal responsibilities. We believe that creative, transformational thinking is needed since, as we wrote in a [previous post](#) [2]: “*Systemic changes that benefit women will improve working conditions for everyone at higher education and research institutions and improve the capacity of our institutions to meet pressing societal challenges.*”

Considering the enormous power of STEMM, and of universities, in shaping our lives, how can we expect to move boldly into the future without benefitting from diverse experience and talents? Unfortunately, even when women and people of color rise to high levels in academia and elsewhere, they often face backlash and intense pressure from beneficiaries of established power structures. This needs to be recognized and stopped.

Every child can benefit from mentoring by a woman in STEMM

Kamala Harris did not follow in her mother’s footsteps; she became a lawyer and a politician rather than a scientist. But, throughout the book, she writes about how profoundly her scientist mother shaped her thinking and her life. Harris saw how hard her mother worked as a cancer researcher while raising her daughters largely as a single mother. She called her mother

extraordinary and wrote that “*She had only two goals in life: to raise her two daughters and to end breast cancer. She pushed us hard and with high expectations as she nurtured us. And all the while, she made Maya and me feel special, like we could do anything we wanted to if we put in the work.*” Through her mother, Harris saw that women could have successful careers, even in male-dominated fields.

Her scientist mother’s influences are apparent throughout the book but especially in Chapter 10, ‘What I’ve learned’ where she shares her insights on leadership. If you don’t have time to read the entire book, read this chapter. The sub-headings are illustrative of her scientist mother’s influences, particularly: ‘Test the Hypothesis’, ‘Go to the Scene’, ‘Show the Math’, and ‘You may be the first. Don’t be the last’.

Harris writes: “... *when you’re the daughter of a scientist, science has a way of shaping how you think. Our mother used to talk to Maya and me about the scientific method as if it were a way of life. When I’d ask her why something was the way it was, she wasn’t content to just give me the answer. She wanted me to formulate my own hypothesis, to use that as a starting point for further investigation, and to challenge my assumptions.*” Learning to think critically is a good thing.

Whether you are a mother or a ‘childless cat lady’, you have the ability as a woman in STEMM to make an impression on every young person you meet. You can demonstrate how to think like a scientist – observing the world, developing and testing hypotheses, gathering and presenting data, understanding what scientists and engineers do, being inquisitive, questioning paradigms, not being afraid of the unknown, and not being afraid to be intelligent. Harris wrote that her mother ‘cooked like a scientist’ and that even when the kitchen experiments didn’t work for a child’s tastebuds, they made her life interesting.

Harris focuses not just on thinking but on doing. “*Years from now, our children and our grandchildren will look up and lock eyes with us. ... I don’t want us to just tell them how we felt. I want us to tell them what we did.*” The world is changing every day, and STEMM is a big part of the changes. We women in STEMM can do so much that we can tell future generations about. It’s up to us to take up Harris’ challenge.

Conclusions and questions for further thought

No matter your nationality or political leanings, we recommend Harris’ book to any woman contemplating or already in leadership. It’s a story worth reading.

Whether or not Kamala Harris wins the presidency is now in the hands of the US electorate, who will decide if they agree with her statement that “*We cannot solve our most intractable problems unless we are honest about what they are, unless we are willing to have difficult conversations and **accept what facts make plain*** (emphasis added).”

If any of our readers are US citizens living abroad, we hope that you realize that you are eligible to vote *even if you have never lived in the US*. A simple, streamlined (and non-partisan) process for registering and requesting your ballot is available [online](#) [4].

Questions for further thought:

- Did you have a mother who was a scientist? If so, how did it affect you?
- How can we improve scientific literacy of non-scientists?
- As a senior woman leader, do you consider yourself a disruptor? If so, how, and why (or why not)?

References and notes

[1] Harris, Kamala, 2019, *The Truths We Hold: An American Journey*, New York, Penguin Press.

[2] <https://www.epistimi.org/blog/its-not-pie-how-equity-for-women-in-stemm-can-benefit-everyone>

[3] <https://www.epistimi.org/blog/the-moment-of-lift-by-melinda-gates>

[4] <https://www.votefromabroad.org/> (Note that you will need the address of your (or your parents') last residence in the US.)